

1 Article

2 Impact of chirp in high-capacity optical metro 3 networks employing directly-modulated VCSELs

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13 **Abstract:** Directly modulated long-wavelength vertical cavity surface emitting lasers (VCSELs) are
14 considered to be exploited to implement sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers for very
15 high capacity transmission (higher than 50 Gb/s per wavelength) in metropolitan area systems
16 characterized by reduced cost, power consumption and footprint. The impact of the frequency chirp
17 measured for InP VCSELs with different kinds of design (high-bandwidth very short cavity and
18 widely-tunable with micro electro-mechanical systems (MEMS) top mirror) is analyzed in case of
19 discrete multitone (DMT) direct modulation in combination with 25-GHz wavelength selective
20 switch (WSS) filtering. The maximum transmitted capacity for both dual side- and single side-band
21 DMT modulation is evaluated as a function of the number of crossed nodes in a mesh metro
22 network, comparing VCSEL based transmitters performance also with the case of external electro-
23 absorption modulator use. Finally, the maximum reach achieved in function of the received optical
24 signal to noise ratio (OSNR) and the fiber span length is discussed. The results confirm the
25 possibility to exploit directly-modulated long-wavelength VCSELs for the realization of sliceable
26 bandwidth/bitrate variable transmitters targeting 50-Gb/s capacity per polarization also in presence
27 of 5 crossed WSSs for hundreds of kilometers reaches in multi-span Erbium doped fiber amplified
28 (EDFA) metro links, supported by coherent detection.

29 **Keywords:** direct modulation; discrete multitone; metro networks; optical communications; vertical
30 cavity surface emitting lasers.

32 1. Introduction

33 In recent years, we are assisting to a continuous growth of bandwidth demand in the access and
34 metropolitan area networks (MANs) as the traffic remains almost confined where it is generated.
35 MANs will then necessarily evolve toward more efficient and agile architectures able to address
36 multi-Tb/s transmission and routing over variable distances and topologies, supporting any kind of
37 services such as 5G, Mobile Edge Computing, ultra-high density TV, etc [1]. Moreover, other
38 challenges should be faced, enabling a “pay-as-you-grow” scheme according to traffic scaling,
39 minimizing the operational expenditures (OpEx) by achieving low footprint and low power
40 consumption. The current transmission devices for metro network are evolving from the traditional
41 approach by proposing enhanced modulation schemes or, as alternative, coherent transmission
42 solution, which today are used mainly for long haul transmission and are characterized by high cost
43 and high-power consumption. With these approaches, the expected performance enhancement in
44 terms of throughput is limited to a factor x2-x4, which seems to be inadequate to support 5G and
45 beyond network requirements. Moreover, a migration towards more flexible, efficient and agile

46 paradigms is expected, owing to the aggregation of the metro/access networks and for the support of
47 heterogeneous networks.

48 Alternative energy- and cost-efficient photonic solutions can be effectively exploited, starting
49 from the adoption of direct modulation (DM) of the laser sources; in particular among them, vertical
50 cavity surface emitting lasers (VCSELs) allow a reduction of transmitter cost, power consumption
51 and footprint. Recently a sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver (S-BVT) based on VCSEL
52 has been proposed for MAN applications [2]. In order to obtain high transmission capacities, long-
53 wavelength InP VCSELs emitting in the C band can be directly modulated by multicarrier formats,
54 such as discrete multitone (DMT) format, as demonstrated for few tens of kms reach with direct
55 detection (DD) [3,4] and for longer reach by DD and single sideband (SSB) modulation [2]. Thanks to
56 bit and power loading at digital signal processing (DSP) level, DMT is capable of addressing the
57 efficient usage of the bandwidth resource as a function of the requested capacity and transmission
58 distance and allowing dynamic and flexible adaptation to traffic/channel conditions and spectrum
59 fragmentation mitigation in MANs [5].

60 Multi-Tb/s transmitters can be obtained by aggregating multiple DM-VCSELs emitting in the C-
61 band with dense wavelength division multiplexers in SOI chips [6,7] providing a fine granularity,
62 e.g. 25 GHz. When the VCSEL is DM to obtain high capacities, the generated frequency chirp impacts
63 significantly on the propagation performance [8], playing an important role especially if the
64 multiplexer filter bandwidths are comparable with the electrical signal bandwidth and potentially
65 limiting the VCSEL employment in high-capacity MAN applications

66 In this paper, long-wavelength VCSEL sources are employed to realize multi-Tb/s transceiver
67 for MAN applications; in particular, we focus the analysis on VCSEL sources emitting in the C-band,
68 taking into account realistic optical sources and network filters. In the following, we analyze the
69 impact of the frequency chirp induced by DM VCSELs when DMT is used to provide a rate higher
70 than 50 Gb/s per wavelength. We take into account both dual side-band (DSB) and single side-band
71 (SSB) DMT modulation while maintaining the modulated optical spectrum confined in 25-GHz
72 spacing to guarantee very dense wavelength-division multiplexing (WDM) transmission. At the
73 receiver side, in order to be able to bridge typical MAN distances, coherent detection (COH-D) is
74 employed, which allows chromatic dispersion (CD) compensation by DSP post-processing.

75 In Section 2 chirp experimental measurements performed on two different kinds of InP long-
76 wavelength VCSELs are presented. In Section 3 the performance for the two measured VCSELs chirp
77 are compared, simulations of transmission employing DMT DM VCSELs and COH-D demonstrate
78 reach distances of hundreds of kms typical of MANs. The considered OSNR are typical of MAN
79 applications, ranging from 30 to 40 dB, which are able to support hundreds-km-long SSMF
80 propagations. Moreover, the impact of wavelength selective switching (WSS) filtering is evaluated as
81 a function of the number of network nodes crossed in the MAN path and of the amount of chirp.
82 Final discussions are drawn in Section 4, concluding the paper.

83 2. Chirp measurements

84 CD leads to a different phase accumulation for each spectral component of a modulated optical
85 signal after fiber propagation. Thanks to coherent detection, the CD cumulated on the whole
86 transmission path can be totally compensated by DSP, removing the distortion on the signal and
87 avoiding significant limitations to the transported capacity, as otherwise appears in case of DD [9].
88 Anyway, the distortion of the received electrical spectrum due to cumulated CD can be exploited to
89 characterize the employed optical source in terms of chirp parameters. Owing to the double-sideband
90 spectrum achieved by DM of the laser, in fact, destructive beating may occur at specific frequencies
91 after the DD process, resulting in a frequency-selective channel that could induce significant
92 distortions on the signal spectrum. The frequency of the fading dips depends on the cumulated CD,
93 moving towards lower frequencies for higher dispersion. Moreover, laser chirp parameters have a
94 strong impact on the shape of the frequency-selective channel, modifying the position and the extent
95 of the spectrum dips [10]. Therefore, a complete characterization of the optical source in terms of
96 chirp properties can be achieved by fitting the uncompensated channel transfer function.

97 The interaction between phase and intensity modulation in a directly-modulated laser is
 98 described using the relation between the instantaneous frequency deviation $\Delta\nu(t)$ and the optical
 99 modulated power $P(t)$ [11]:

$$\Delta\nu(t) = \frac{\alpha}{4\pi} \left(\frac{1}{P(t)} \frac{\partial P(t)}{\partial t} + \kappa P(t) \right), \quad (1)$$

100 where α is the linewidth enhancement factor and κ is the laser-specific adiabatic constant related to
 101 thermal effects, which depends on several laser parameters such as its gain saturation, carrier lifetime
 102 and confinement factor. The first term of Eq. (1), which mainly depends on the α factor, is the transient
 103 component, while the second one is the adiabatic chirp, which depends on the κ factor. A small-signal
 104 frequency response analysis can be exploited for modeling the optical source and obtain its specific
 105 chirp coefficients [12]. For a directly modulated laser (DML), the general channel transfer function
 106 can be expressed as [10]:

$$H(\omega) = \left| \cos(\theta) - \sin(\theta) \alpha \left(1 - j \frac{\omega_c}{\omega} \right) \right|, \quad (2)$$

107 where

$$\theta = \frac{LD\lambda_0^2\omega^2}{4\pi c}, \quad \omega_c = \kappa P_0, \quad (3)$$

108 and L is the fiber length, D the dispersion coefficient, λ_0 the wavelength of the CW source, c the
 109 speed of light and P_0 the mean optical power. The position of the frequency dips and the height of
 110 the secondary lobes are determined by an interplay of α and D , while the extent of the dips (in
 111 particular of the first one) is primarily due to ω_c , i.e. to the adiabatic component of the chirp.

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Figure 1. Experimental setup for chirp parameters measurement.

114 This analysis technique has been used for measuring the chirp parameters of two different
 115 devices: the first is a 20-GHz long-wavelength VCSEL emitting at 1533.4 nm [13], while the second is
 116 an 8-GHz VCSEL tunable over about 70 nm in the third fiber window [14]. The former device is based
 117 on a short-cavity design, while the latter exploits a micro electro-mechanical systems (MEMS) top-
 118 mirror to achieve its very wide tunability. The two devices show different chirp performance, owing
 119 to their specific technology.

Figure 2. Channel transfer functions obtained after 10-km (blue), 24-km (red) and 34-km (yellow) SSMF propagation for: (a) 8-GHz tunable VCSEL and (b) 20-GHz short-cavity VCSEL.

The experimental setup exploited for VCSEL chirp parameter estimation is shown in Figure 1. In particular, the long-wavelength VCSEL is directly modulated by a vector network analyzer with 40-GHz bandwidth, which generates the RF signal to perform the small-signal modulation analysis. The VCSEL bias is 9 mA and 16 mA for the fixed and tunable devices, emitting around 2.5 mW and 0.9 mW, respectively. In case of the tunable VCSEL, the MEMS bias is fixed to 20 mA while the temperature is maintained at 25°C by a standard temperature controller. The optical signal then propagates in a standard single-mode fiber (SSMF) coil and is received by an EDFA preamplifier followed by a p-intrinsic-n (PIN) photodiode with 25-GHz electrical bandwidth; a variable optical attenuator (VOA) allows to perform the measurements at constant received power. The SSMF length ranges from 10 km to 34 km in order to change the cumulated CD at the receiver end.

At first the optical back-to-back contribution featuring the spectral distortions due to the electro/optic (E/O) and opto/electronic (O/E) processes is measured and excluded in order to measure only the fiber power transfer function (i.e. removing the VCSEL and receiver transfer functions). Eq. (2) is used to fit the obtained curves; the measured (continuous curves) and theoretical (dashed curves) frequency responses for the tunable and short-cavity VCSEL sources are shown in Figure 2a) and Figure 2b) on 10-GHz and 25-GHz ranges, respectively. The different frequency ranges have been chosen owing to the different E/O bandwidths. As expected, when the cumulated dispersion increases the frequency dips move towards lower frequencies, reducing the electrical spectrum undistorted region. However, a difference in the position and the depth of the first frequency dip for the two lasers clearly appears, confirming the different chirp regime of the two devices. The tunable VCSEL, in fact, is mainly limited by the transient chirp, while the short-cavity device shows even a significant adiabatic chirp, as visible by the limited extent of the first frequency dip, which almost disappears for 24-km and 34-km SSMF channel transfer functions. The theoretical curves after fitting (dashed lines in Figure 2) show a good agreement with the experimental measurements, allowing a reliable estimation of VCSEL chirp parameters in both cases, reported in Table 1. The short-cavity VCSEL shows higher α and κ factors, as expected from the device design based on a short-cavity technology. This laser design permits to achieve wide modulation bandwidth, but a strong frequency chirp is induced during direct modulation, limiting its effectiveness in presence of network nodes with narrow channel bandwidth.

Table 1. Measured chirp parameters of the two VCSEL sources.

	α	κ
Tunable VCSEL	2.75	$8.3 \cdot 10^{12}$
Short-cavity VCSEL	3.7	$1.52 \cdot 10^{13}$

155 3. Simulations

156 As previously demonstrated, InP long-wavelength VCSELs can show different amount of chirp,
 157 depending on their design and fabrication. When analyzing the transmission performance of DM-
 158 VCSELs this parameter plays a critical role especially in the presence of filtering associated to
 159 wavelength multiplexers and demultiplexers present inside the WDM MAN, e.g at the network
 160 nodes. It has to be noticed, in fact, that the chirp interplay with CD can be neglected in case of COH-
 161 D exploitation, where CD DSP compensation can be easily performed. Moreover, as DM is exploited,
 162 the transmitted signal is just intensity modulated and a simplified coherent receiver can be used [15]:
 163 after I and Q components recovery and CD compensation the I and Q square moduli are performed
 164 and summed up in order to obtain the originally transmitted intensity signal. This approach avoids
 165 the use of phase and frequency recovery, reducing the complexity of the receiver DSP and also
 166 relaxing the constraints on VCSEL and local oscillator (LO) linewidths. As a drawback this operation
 167 cancels the advantages in terms of bit error rate (BER) as a function of signal to noise ratio (SNR) of
 168 COH-D.

169 Our simulations are obtained developing a modeling tool based on Matlab™ which includes all
 170 the transmitter, propagation and receiver blocks. Specifically, the COH receiver exploits a 10-dBm
 171 per polarization LO with 100-kHz linewidth and has 25-GHz electrical bandwidth. The DM VCSEL
 172 is modeled considering both the intrinsic modulation properties and the extrinsic device parasitic
 173 components. The overall electrical modulation frequency response can be described by [16]:

$$H(f) = H_{int}(f) \cdot H_{par}(f) = \text{const} \cdot \frac{f_R^2}{f_R^2 + j \frac{\gamma}{2\pi} f - f^2} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + j \frac{f}{f_p}} \quad (4)$$

174 where f_R is the relaxation resonance frequency, γ is the intrinsic damping factor and f_p is the
 175 parasitic cut-off frequency.

176 The simulations have been performed for three different chirp conditions, corresponding to the
 177 following three cases:

- 178 1. a directly-modulated VCSEL with chirp parameters as the short-cavity device
- 179 2. a directly-modulated VCSEL with chirp parameters as the tunable device
- 180 3. a CW 500-kHz laser followed by an electro-absorption modulator (EAM) with $\alpha = 0.4$

181 For all the three cases, following [16] and Eq. (4), the modulation frequency bandwidth is set to
 182 18 GHz, although this bandwidth is now achieved only by the actual short-cavity devices. The VCSEL
 183 linewidth is 5 MHz, which is a suitable value for both long-wavelength VCSELs. The bias currents
 184 are set to 8 mA and 16 mA for case 1) and 2), respectively, while their modulation amplitudes are
 185 8.5 mA and 26 mA respectively; thanks to the reduced amount of chirp, in fact, in the tunable VCSEL
 186 case it is possible to exploit a higher modulation depth, allowing higher SNRs. The bias current and
 187 the modulation depth for case 3) are optimized in order to achieve an equivalent extinction ratio
 188 of 15 dB.

189 The impact of optical filtering is evaluated using the transfer function of a 25-GHz channel
 190 spacing WSS, which shows a 21-GHz full width half maximum (FWHM) [9]. The propagation
 191 medium is a SSF, with 0.25 dB/km attenuation and 17 ps/nm km dispersion at 1550 nm. Fiber spans
 192 of 35 km and 65 km are considered with the employment of Erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (EDFAs)
 193 with 6-dB noise figure (NF) to compensate for the transmission losses of each span.

194 The performance is evaluated in case of DMT modulation signals, considering DSB and SSB
 195 transmissions; in both conditions, the generated optical spectra have to occupy less than 25 GHz in
 196 order to be transmitted through cascaded WSSs, guaranteeing 25-GHz WDM spacing for fine
 197 granularity. For this reason, we tested a DSB DMT signal composed by 256 sub-carriers in 10 GHz
 198 range, i.e. the sub-carrier spacing is 39.062 MHz; occupying an optical bandwidth of around 20 GHz;
 199 a cyclic prefix (CP) of about 2.1% of the symbol length is also added. On the other hand, the SSB
 200 transmission is performed by properly detuning the WSS with respect to the carrier of a DMT signal
 201 composed by 256 sub-carriers in 20 GHz range, i.e. the sub-carrier spacing is 78.125 MHz; again a CP
 202 of about 2.1% of the symbol length is added. Figure 3 shows the spectrum of the SSB signal obtained

203 detuning the WSS in order to select half of the 20-GHz DMT DSB spectrum, while preserving the
 204 optical carrier.

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 206 **Figure 3.** DMT SSB optical spectrum (red), obtained by a 9.5-GHz detuned WSS (orange) filtering of
 207 a DMT DSB signal with 20-GHz electrical bandwidth and 40 -GHz optical bandwidth (blue).

208 As can be seen, in order to mimic a realistic WSS transfer function with limited extinction, we
 209 imposed a maximum out-of-band attenuation of 40 dB. The left side of the optical spectrum is
 210 correctly filtered out, while a slight impact on the last subcarriers on the right appears due to the 21-
 211 GHz FWHM.

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 213 **Figure 4.** a-f) Tunable VCSEL: DSB DMT (10 GHz) for single WSS filtering and 40-dB OSNR. a)
 214 Received electrical spectrum b) Bit loading and corresponding EVM c) BER per subcarrier d) Bit-
 215 loading SNR e-f) Examples of received constellations.

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Figure 5. a)-f) Tunable VCSEL: SSB DMT for single WSS filtering (9.5-GHz detuned) and 40-dB OSNR. a) Received electrical spectrum b) Bit loading and corresponding EVM c) BER per subcarrier d) Bit-loading SNR e)-f) Examples of received constellations.

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Together with CD compensation, the receiver DSP provides digital symbol synchronization, CP removal, sub-carriers phase recovery, demodulation and error count. In the following the transmitted capacity is evaluated performing Chow’s bit loading algorithm [17] with a target BER of $3.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (corresponding to 7% overhead hard decision FEC limit) for single-channel, single-polarization transmission. Figure 4 a)-f) shows an example of the results obtained for DSB DMT modulation of the tunable VCSEL ($\alpha=2.75 \kappa=8.3 \cdot 10^{12}$) in case of one WSS filtering and 40-dB OSNR. Figure 4 a)-f) reports the received electrical spectrum, the bit loading, the BER per subcarrier and examples of received constellations.

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Figure 5 a)-f) reports the same graphs for the tunable VCSEL SSB DMT transmission in case of one WSS filtering and 40-dB OSNR for a WSS detuning of 9.5 GHz with respect to the VCSEL carrier. By comparing the received spectra, it is evident that SSB has a higher spectral efficiency, exploiting all the available VCSEL bandwidth and filling the whole 25-GHz channel bandwidth with the multicarrier signal. On the other hand, as expected, SSB suffers more of signal-signal beating interference (SSBI) [18] and of VCSEL and WSS bandwidth limitations: in fact, at low and high frequencies SSB modulation presents lower SNRs with respect to the central frequencies (Figure 5d)) and first and last subcarriers can support constellations with a lower level number, i.e. lower bit/symbol (Figure 5 b), e) and f)). DSB modulation, instead, presents a flat SNR over all the subcarriers, supporting 6 or 7 bit per symbol per subcarrier; nevertheless, only half of the available E/O spectrum can be occupied in order to fit the 25-GHz optical spectrum constraint, limiting the maximum achievable capacity.

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Figure 6 shows the capacities achieved for OSNR ranging from 30 dB to 40 dB in function of the number of crossed WSS in case of DSB DMT (Figure 6 a)) and in case of SSB DMT (Figure 6 b)). The results are reported for the two different chirp conditions considered so far. For comparison, also the transmission capacities achieved for DSB and SSB DMT modulation in case of chirp typical of electro-absorption modulated lasers (EML), i.e. $\alpha=0.4$, are reported in Figure 7a) and b) respectively. As can be seen by comparing Figure 6 dashed curves and continuous curves the tunable VCSEL performance are better than the short-cavity VCSEL one, due to the lower chirp parameters. This is particularly true for DSB modulation and is confirmed by Figure 7 a) where the chirp of the EML is even lower. On the other hand, this is less evident for SSB modulation where only for a higher number of crossed WSS the short-cavity VCSEL transported capacities are significantly lower than the tunable VCSEL

250 ones, i.e. when chirp-filtering interaction is more detrimental. Moreover, by comparing Figure 6 b)
 251 and Figure 7 b) it can be noticed that, in case of lower OSNRs, a limited amount of chirp could be
 252 useful, since the performance of the EML are worse than the VCSELs. This effect could be due to the
 253 decrease of the carrier to signal power ratio (CSPR) in presence of chirp. CSPR has a strong impact
 254 on the capacity of DMT-modulated signal [19]; hence, its reduction due to chirp could mitigate the
 255 capacity decrease in the SSB condition.

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Figure 6. Transmission capacities vs number of crossed WSS for: 40-dB OSNR (blue square), 35-dB OSNR (red circle), 30-dB OSNR (green triangle), and short-cavity VCSEL (continuous line open symbols), tunable VCSEL (dashed line full symbol) a) DSB DMT modulation. b) SSB DMT modulation.

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Figure 7. Transmission capacities vs number of crossed WSS for EML: 40-dB OSNR (blue square), 35-dB OSNR (red circle), 30-dB OSNR (green triangle). a) DSB DMT modulation. b) SSB DMT modulation.

265 Finally, Table 2 and Table 3 summarize the transmitted capacities and SSF reach as a function
 266 of the span length and of the number of crossed WSS respectively for DSB and SSB DMT modulations
 267 for the VCSEL based transmitters. The results are very encouraging for the exploitation of VCSELs in
 268 S-BVT transmitters targeting around 50 Gb/s capacity per polarization in presence of COH-D. In fact,
 269 especially for SSB DMT modulation also in presence of 5 WSS consecutive filtering more than 50 Gb/s

270 data rates are expected for OSNRs above 30 dB. This allows to bridge more than 250 km SSMF when
 271 using EDFAs with typical NF performance and span length of 65 km; with shorter span length even
 272 longer transmission distances can be supported covering indeed wider MANs. However, DMT DSB
 273 performance is heavily impaired by chirp and its interplay with filtering, limiting the achievable
 274 capacities below 50 Gb/s also for 100-km transmission ranges.

275 **Table 2.** Transmitted capacities and SSMF reach for SSB DMT as a function of: span length, VCSEL
 276 type/ chirp, and number of crossed WSS.

		OSNR	40 dB	35 dB	30 dB
Reach	35-km span		70 km	210 km	735 km
	65-km span		---	65 km	260 km
Short-cavity VCSEL	Capacity w 1 WSS		78.6 Gb/s	72.6 Gb/s	57.3 Gb/s
	Capacity w 3 WSS		68.6 Gb/s	63.1 Gb/s	54.5 Gb/s
	Capacity w 5 WSS		61 Gb/s	58.4 Gb/s	50.5 Gb/s
Tunable VCSEL	Capacity w 1 WSS		76.2 Gb/s	70 Gb/s	56.2 Gb/s
	Capacity w 3 WSS		73.3 Gb/s	67 Gb/s	55 Gb/s
	Capacity w 5 WSS		70.4 Gb/s	63.8 Gb/s	54.Gb/s

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278 **Table 3.** Transmitted capacities and SSMF reach for DSB DMT as a function of: span length, VCSEL
 279 type/ chirp, and number of crossed WSS.

		OSNR	40 dB	35 dB	30 dB
Reach	35-km span		70 km	210 km	735 km
	65-km span		---	65 km	260 km
Short-cavity VCSEL	Capacity w 1 WSS		45.5 Gb/s	30.9 Gb/s	22.8 Gb/s
	Capacity w 3 WSS		35.3 Gb/s	27.5 Gb/s	19.9 Gb/s
	Capacity w 5 WSS		31.1 Gb/s	25.2 Gb/s	19.2 Gb/s
Tunable VCSEL	Capacity w 1 WSS		61.2 Gb/s	51 Gb/s	34 Gb/s
	Capacity w 3 WSS		52.6 Gb/s	47.8 Gb/s	32.4 Gb/s
	Capacity w 5 WSS		48 Gb/s	43.75 Gb/s	30 Gb/s

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281 **4. Discussion and conclusions**

282 We proposed to exploit directly modulated long-wavelength VCSELs to implement S-BVT for
 283 capacity transmission higher than 50 Gb/s per wavelength in metropolitan area systems characterized
 284 by reduced cost, power consumption and footprint. The most significant drawback of the direct
 285 modulation of VCSELs is frequency chirp, in particular when associated to optical filtering as in the
 286 network nodes. Thus, we analyzed its impact in case of dense WDM (25-GHz) WSS filtering in a
 287 DMT-based transmission system with direct modulation of the optical source and coherent detection
 288 at the receiver end to compensate for the cumulated chromatic dispersion. The performance

289 evaluation by suitable simulations has been performed both in case of DSB and SSB transmissions.
290 Since an optical bandwidth of 25 GHz can be filled up, a 10-GHz DSB and a 20-GHz SSB signals have
291 been used. In order to obtain the chirp parameters to be used in reliable simulations for the
292 transmission performance evaluation, preliminary measurements on InP VCSELs with two designs
293 (a high-bandwidth device based on a short-cavity technology and a widely-tunable laser with MEMS
294 top mirror) have been performed. A third case including the exploitation of an EML was added for
295 reference; in order to focus on the chirp impact only, the remaining simulation parameters have been
296 maintained unchanged for all the considered cases, in particular the modulation bandwidth was set
297 to 18 GHz. The maximum transmitted capacity for both DSB and SSB DMT modulation were
298 evaluated as a function of the number of crossed nodes in a mesh metro network, and of the received
299 OSNR. The results indicate that, especially for many WSS crossings, in case of DSB modulation lower
300 chirp parameters allow higher capacities, whereas in case of SSB modulation and lower OSNR the
301 presence of a limited amount of chirp supports better performance, in particular for lower OSNR
302 values (close to 30 dB). The presence of frequency chirp associated to direct modulation broadens the
303 spectral occupancy in the optical domain. In case of DSB transmission, the optical filter is perfectly
304 centered on the VCSEL carrier, and the best results can be achieved by a chirp-free optical signal,
305 which shows an optical spectrum with minimum bandwidth. On the other hand, in case of SSB
306 transmission the frequency chirp superimposed on the signal permits to reduce the CSPR with
307 respect to the chirp-free condition, leading to an enhancement of the system performance. A trade-
308 off between the amount of chirp and the SSB filter bandwidth to reach the optimal condition could
309 be found, so further theoretical, simulative and experimental analyses are ongoing. Transmitters
310 hosting devices characterized by chirp parameters as the tunable VCSEL and exploiting 20-GHz SSB
311 DMT modulation would thus support higher capacities; however, such a device is not actually
312 available, since only the short-cavity technology is now able to guarantee modulation bandwidths
313 higher than 10 GHz, needed to fully take advantage of the SSB spectral efficiency.

314 Finally, the maximum reach achieved in function of the received OSNR and the fiber span length
315 was discussed. The results confirm the possibility to exploit directly-modulated long-wavelength
316 VCSELs for the realization of transmitters targeting 50-Gb/s capacity per polarization also in presence
317 of 5 crossed WSSs for hundreds of kilometers reaches in multi-span EDFA-amplified metro links,
318 supported by coherent detection.

319 The reported simulative analysis shows that the VCSEL-based optical communication system
320 envisaged for metro area networks could represent a suitable solution to reach multi Tb/s capacities
321 simultaneously decreasing costs, footprint and power consumption with respect to traditional
322 approaches based on I/Q modulation and standard coherent detection. Moreover, the proposed
323 architecture can be easily adapted also to short-reach and datacenters scenarios exploiting the O-band
324 of the optical communications. In this wavelength range, thanks to the limited impact of chromatic
325 dispersion, even direct detection could be a suitable option, further reducing costs, footprint, power
326 consumption and complexity of the transmission system.

327

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